

Phenyl-4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl Diketones

V. S. Bhagwat and K. S. Nargund

Phenylglyoxal was condensed with benzoyl chloride in presence of potassium cyanide and the cyanohydrin obtained was converted into α -benzyloxy- α -benzoylthioacetamide by hydrogen sulphide. This was then condensed with substituted *w*-bromoacetophenones. The thiazoles obtained, on hydrolysis and oxidation gave phenyl-4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl diketones.

Various methods of preparing phenyl thiazolyl diketones are under investigation in this laboratory. Preparation of phenyl 2-phenyl-4-thiazolyl diketones has been described in the previous communication¹. In the present investigation phenyl-4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl diketones are described by the following series of reactions.

Where R=H; CH₃; Cl; OCH₃;

and

R'=H or Cl

Phenylglyoxal was condensed with benzoylchloride in presence of potassium cyanide to obtain benzoyl derivative of phenylglyoxalcyanohydrin(I)^{2,3}. This was then treated with hydrogen sulphide in alcoholic solution containing triethanolamine to obtain α -benzoyloxy- α -benzoylthioacetamide(II). This was then condensed with substituted w-bromoacetophenones in alcoholic solution to obtain benzoyl derivatives of 4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl benzoyl carbinols (III).

Hydrolysis of these in cold alcoholic potassium hydroxide gave the corresponding carbinols(IV). Carbinols on oxidation with potassium dichromate in acetic acid gave the diketones(V). The diketones were characterised by preparing their quinoxaline derivatives.

Substituted phenylglyoxals did not condense with benzoylchloride in presence of potassium cyanide.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the benzoyl derivative of phenylglyoxal cyanohydrin. 14.05 gm(0.1 M) of benzoylchloride were added to 13.4 gm (0.1M) of phenylglyoxal contained in a 250 ml round bottom flask. The mixture was cooled in ice bath. Saturated solution of potassium cyanide 6.5 gm(0.1 M) in water was added drop by drop to the above mixture with vigorous shaking, taking care not to allow the temperature to rise. It was then allowed to stand overnight. The pale yellow semisolid product was repeatedly washed with water. It was used further without purification.

Preparation of α -benzoyloxy- α -Benzoylthioacetamide. The above crude product was dissolved in alcohol (75 ml) and filtered from insoluble colourless material. To the filtrate 2 ml of triethanolamine were added and dry hydrogen sulphide gas was passed through it for 4 hr. The flask was corked tightly and kept overnight. The colourless crystalline thioamide was filtered, washed with alcohol and crystallised from alcohol-benzene mixture. Colourless shining plates, m.p.188°; yield 7.0 gm.

(Found N=4.60% ; C₁₆H₁₃NO₃S requires N=4.68%).

Benzoyl derivatives of 4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl benzoyl carbinols : 15 gm(0.05 M) of the thioamide and substituted w-bromoacetophenones (0.05M) were mixed with alcohol (100 ml). The mixture was refluxed on water bath for 3 hr. when a clear solution resulted. It was then diluted with water and neutralised with ten percent solution of sodium bicarbonate. The solids separated were filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol-benzene mixture. (Table 1)

4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl benzoyl carbinols. 10 gm of the benzoyl derivatives were added to 100 ml of 3% alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution, when a dark green colour developed. The mixture was stirred for half an hour when the colour changed to light orange. It was then allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 hrs. Contents were then diluted with water and the gummy mass separated was used for further reaction without purification.

2. Olin and Johnson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1470-75.

3. Francis *et al*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 1404.

TABLE I

No	R	R ₁	Formula	Properties	Analysis	
					Found	Reqd.
1.	H	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ NO ₃ S	Colourless shining flakes, m.p. 131-32°.	N=3.42	3.51
2.	CH ₃	H	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ NO ₃ S	Colourless shining needles, m.p. 110-111°.	N=3.31	3.39
3.	Cl	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ ClNO ₃ S	Yellow shining plates, m.p. 121-122°.	Cl=8.06	8.19
4.	OCH ₃	H	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ NO ₄ S	Yellow prisms, m.p. 136-37°.	N=3.19	3.26
5.	Cl	Cl (3)	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ NO ₃ S	Yellow microneedles, m.p. 128-129°.	Cl=15.01	15.17
6.	Cl	Cl(2)	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ NO ₃ S	Yellow shining plates, m.p. 128-129°.	Cl=15.08	15.17
7.	Cl(2)	Cl(5)	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ NO ₃ S	Pale yellow shining plates, m.p. 105-106°.	Cl=15.1	15.17

All the compounds were crystallised from alcohol-benzene mixture.

Phenyl-4-phenyl-2-thiazolyl diketones. The above carbinols were dissolved in 50 ml of acetic acid and 2.5 gm of potassium dichromate dissolved in minimum quantity of water were added to it. The mixture was heated on steam bath for 3 hr. The contents were diluted with water and the red oily compounds were extracted with ether. Ether was removed and the products crystallised from alcohol. They were characterised by the preparation of quinoxaline derivatives.

TABLE II

No	R	R ₁	Formula	Properties	Analysis	
					Found	Reqd.
1.	H	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ NO ₂ S	Pale yellow plates, m.p. 112-13°.	N=4.67	4.78
Quinoxaline			C ₂₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ S	*Pale yellow microneedles, m.p. 212-13°.	N=11.39	11.51
2.	CH ₃	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NO ₂ S	Pale yellow flakes, m.p. 109-110°.	N=4.48	4.56
Quinoxaline			C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	Yellow needles, m.p. 188-189°.	N=11.0	11.08
3.	Cl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ ClNO ₂ S	Pale yellow thick plates, m.p. 105-106°.	Cl=10.71	10.84
Quinoxaline			C ₂₃ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ S	Yellow needles, m.p. 217-218°.	Cl=8.78	8.89
4.	OCH ₃	H	—	Not isolated	—	—
Quinoxaline			C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	Yellow needles, m.p. 157-158°.	N=10.54	10.63
5.	Cl	Cl (3)	C ₁₇ H ₉ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 62-63°.	Cl=19.55	19.62
Quinoxaline			C ₂₃ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ S	*Pale yellow needles, m.p. 214-215°.	Cl=16.28	16.36
6.	Cl	Cl (2)	—	Not isolated	—	—
Quinoxaline			C ₂₃ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ S	Yellow crystals, m.p. 205-206°.	Cl=16.22	16.36
7.	Cl (2)	Cl(5)	C ₁₇ H ₉ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	Pale yellow flat needles, m.p. 97-98°.	Cl=19.51	19.62
Quinoxaline			C ₂₃ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ S	*Pale yellow microneedles, m.p. 211-212°.	Cl=16.25	16.36

*Crystallised from alcohol benzene mixture. Rest from alcohol.